

FAIRness of published data in life sciences, and opportunities to improve

[D4.1 A report describing best practices of literature biocuration CH-SIB M12]

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Abstract

There's a growing trend to publish data in generalist repositories, such as Zenodo or Dryad, as well as supplementary data files alongside articles. A potential gold mine, this vast data resource is still under-utilised. This report examines each FAIR principle (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of the "long tail of data" in life sciences, focusing on both published data and annotated publications, and proposes recommendations for key actors to improve the current state.

1. Introduction

Exponential amount of published data. Scientific publication remains the primary channel of communication in the life sciences and is growing exponentially (Bornmann et al., 2021, Hanson et al, 2024). This traditional model is, however, associated with delays to the release of information to the community (Penfold and Polka, 2020) and there is increasing pressure to change the scientific publication model from "curate first, publish second" (traditional peer review) to "publish first, curate second" approaches (e.g. use of preprint servers and open peer review; Stern & O'Shea, 2019).

Although there is a long standing history of subject specific deposition databases that provide homes for much of the data produced during experimentation process to enable better sharing and reuse (see <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/core-data-resources>; <https://globalbiodata.org/what-we-do/global-core-biodata-resources/list-of-current-global-core-biodata-resources/>), such data is generally released for public consumption at the time of the associated article publication and not beforehand, for instance at the time of preprint posting, during the publication peer review process, or even earlier. Changes to the publication model, as proposed, would also require data to be made open at the start of the

publication process too, to ensure effective peer review assessment of all aspects of the output, including this associated data.

A combination of the exponential growth in journal article publications and open science practices evolving with pressure to release and openly publish all data generated during the experimental process, irrespective of whether it fits a specialist data repository, has resulted in a growing number of publications to generalist data repositories such as Zenodo, Dryad or BioStudies, as well as increase in supplemental data files (Pop & Salzberg, 2015; Vale, 2015). This vast and often underutilized resource, commonly referred to as the “long tail of data”, represents a significant opportunity for scientific progress, but faces challenges in management, sharing, and reuse (Heidorn, 2008 ; Ferguson et al., 2014).

Need for FAIR published data. The FAIR principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (Wilkinson et al., 2016) are gaining ground in life sciences to tackle these challenges and maximize the value of published data (Boeckhout et al., 2018). The FAIR Cookbook has emerged as a valuable resource to guide researchers and data managers in implementing FAIR principles. But despite growing endorsement, practical implementation remains challenging, and many key data sources are not easily usable for automated workflows and integrated analyses (Rocca-Serra et al., 2023). An assessment of popular life sciences open data sources revealed that significant effort is still required to enhance their FAIRness and integrate them into semantic web-based platforms (Pattyn et al., 2017).

Scope of this report. This report examines the FAIRness of the long tail of data in the life science, focusing on both published data and annotated publications, and proposes recommendations for key actors to enhance the current state. These key actors are depicted in Figure 1. Funder mandates enforce publishers and authors to respond to requirements and change their practices. Authors and publishers play a central role by generating, reviewing and disseminating research data. Biocurators contribute by reviewing the literature and semantically linking outputs hidden within supplementary files and generalist data deposits to database entries, and can enhance publications with annotations that utilize standard ontologies, dictionaries and data persistent identifiers. Data platforms serve as repositories for aggregating and managing this data, and empower users with search engines and text mining solutions. While each actor works within their own specific context and data representations, understanding how they share data and identifying opportunities for improvement, collaboration and interoperability is crucial for maximizing their value and accessibility.

Further, the report focuses on life science data. We do consider generalist deposition services, however we focus on not for profit services with large proportions of biological data. These criteria exclude service providers such as Figshare or Dryad.

Figure 1. Data exchanges between key actors in the Life Sciences.

2. How FAIR are published data in life sciences ?

To evaluate the adherence of shared data to the FAIR principles, we will examine each aspect (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) using Boeckhout's comprehensive definitions (Boeckhout et al., 2018). Our evaluation will involve a combination of methods, including:

- explicit verification: examining how the FAIR principles are explicitly applied today in the data sharing process.
- quantitative analysis: conducting quantitative assessments of the data to measure its adherence to FAIR principles, and how it has evolved in the last decade.
- stakeholder perspectives: gathering insights from key actors involved in data sharing to understand their experiences, challenges, and perspectives on FAIR data practices.

2.1 Findability

« Datasets should be described, identified and registered or indexed in a clear and unequivocal manner. »

2.1.1 Metadata standards adopted

Presentation of different metadata standards. There has been a positive trend towards the adoption of metadata standards for life sciences data. However, the current landscape presents a challenge: the existence of multiple standards, such as BioSharing (McQuilton et al., 2016), schema.org (Patel-Schneider et al., 2014), BioSchema (Gray et al., 2017) or the DataCite Metadata Schema (Ammann et al., 2019), can hinder interoperability and consistency in data discovery and utilization.

Publishing practices. Publisher engagement in FAIR data has centred on data citation principles (Martone et al., 2014; Cousijn et al., 2018) and despite efforts to guide publishers

in how to mark up data citations in the bibliography (NISO JATS4R working group, 2020) and data availability statements (NISO JATS4R working group, 2018), progress has been limited. Additionally, the use of supplementary files posted on the publisher platform as a method to limit the size of an article and enable sharing of data is also a common practice and this affects findability not least due to link rot and loss of data (Briney 2024), but also because there is no independent method to cite the supplementary material with a persistent identifier that is independent of the article itself.

Metadata in Zenodo. Zenodo explicitly adheres to the DataCite Metadata Schema and enforces metadata completion at the time of deposition, which could ensure its datasets are described with FAIR metadata. However, it is a general purpose repository containing materials from accepted manuscripts and preprints to peer reviews and software. Beyond the minimum and recommended terms, Zenodo may incorporate additional enrichments to provide more detailed information about datasets, such as domain-specific metadata or provenance information, further enhancing their value and accessibility. However, this requires author engagement to populate the fields, which is problematic even for subject specific repositories where the value of the metadata is presumably better understood.

Metadata in Dryad. Dryad is a dataset repository dedicated to data, unlike Zenodo. It is also multidisciplinary and explicitly adheres to the DataCite Metadata Schema and enforces the metadata completion at the time of deposition. It also collaborates and integrates with many publisher systems to cross populate metadata fields and coordinate publication of data at the time of article publication and provides reviewer links for access to assess datasets during the peer review process. However, like Zenodo it is a generalist repository and does not contain additional metadata fields to further categorize content and suffers the same issues within a publisher citation workflow, although it does recommend the data is cited in the bibliography and provides details on how to do so.

Metadata in PMC. In contrast, while PMC includes metadata for publications, it lacks a mechanism to describe the supplementary data files themselves beyond the author-provided descriptions in the manuscript. This makes it impossible to search for data contained in PMC supplementary files without searching for information on the article itself.

Metadata in BioStudies. Through a collaboration between Europe PMC and BioStudies, a general purpose data repository for life sciences outputs, all supplemental files available with open access research articles in Europe PMC are deposited in BioStudies. BioStudies provides schema.org markup, and offers an extensible metadata mechanism, though for this data ingestion pipeline the extent of metadata is limited.

2.1.2 Persistent identifiers for articles and datasets

PIDs for publications - Medline. For publications, a Crossref DOI is primarily used, and its usage is becoming increasingly prevalent in life science. In MEDLINE, while internal identifiers (PMIDs) are assigned to all indexed citations, DOIs are not systematically specified. However, quantitative studies indicate an increasing trend in publications with DOIs, from 50% in 1980 more than 99% today, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Percentage of citations with a specified DOI in MEDLINE, according to publication year.

PIDs for Zenodo and Dryad datasets. DataCite DOIs are used for datasets deposited to those repositories. However, it's important to note that these DOIs identify the record-level entity (publication or dataset) rather than individual files. Additionally, research on publisher categorisation of software citations in Zenodo co-incidentally demonstrates publishers do not categorise Datacite DOI datasets in their reference lists correctly, mislabelling them as journal articles in the main (PMC Europe, 2022). It is hypothesized this is the result of publishing citation verification workflows being built on checking the Crossref API for DOIs and not engaging in DataCite, thereby miscategorising DOIs when assigned a DataCite DOI. Despite this, publishing practices focus on the DOI as the main persistent identifier they recognise for addition to bibliographic information so although miscategorised, datasets with DataCite DOIs can make it into the reference list. However, this limits the capability to properly cite accession numbers, which are the mainstay of life sciences data deposition databases. As cited by (Ross et al., 2024), "the number of accession numbers generated for European Nucleotide Archive records alone (3.8 billion accessions) exceeds the total number of DOIs registered with Crossref (164.24 million DOIs)".

PIDs for supplementary datasets. In the main, datasets contained within the supplementary article files, the DOI or the PMCID associated with the publication is the only mechanism of identification. Some publishers, for example F1000, PLOS and eLife, assign Crossref component DOIs to their supplementary files as a means to enable separate citation. However, this is not well handled by the Crossref API and so has limited utility and has not seen usage in citation metrics. Files could be uniquely identified by their names, but they are discretionary and have no standardization; PMC only states that "names of image files and supplemental data files must match the names referenced in the XML file". A robust approach for obtaining PIDs at file-level involves combining the record identifier with the file name. Unfortunately, this practice is not standard.

PIDs in BioStudies. Supplemental files deposited in BioStudies from the collaboration with Europe PMC are assigned an Accession number, which is linked back to Europe PMC. It's important to note that these accessions identify the record-level entity (publication or dataset) rather than individual files. Submissions direct to BioStudies are assigned a Crossref DOI. In 2018, SIBiLS attempted a similar process by assigning ARK IDs to individual PMC supplementary data files, but scalability challenges limited the adoption of this approach. While these approaches are commendable and have potential value, unless author submitted datasets assigned a DOI, the accessions are implemented after the publication

process and is not apparent on other platforms (or by publisher or authors themselves) so although the supplementary files have been given a persistent identifier, their usage is limited.

2.1.3 Specialized search engines

Specialized search engines for life sciences are designed to efficiently discover datasets by indexing and searching metadata. To enhance search accuracy, these engines may incorporate advanced features such as metadata-based filtering, relevance ranking, and plain text search. Examples of specialized search engines for datasets in the life sciences field include Zenodo, Biodiversity PMC, Europe PMC and BioStudies.

Zenodo. In Zenodo, metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in a dedicated search engine immediately after publishing. Records can be searched by keywords, ranked by relevance, date or popularity, and by some metadata such as file types or license. Additionally, metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers and indexed there.

Biodiversity PMC. Biodiversity PMC allows for such searches, including relevance and chronological ranking, filtering by license or file type, and even plain text search within extracted file content, enabled by text mining.

Europe PMC. Text-based supplemental file content has been text and data mined for biomedical entities and data accessions. These are available in search and thereby any relevant information identified in the supplemental files is surfaced to users. On the article page, the location of the entity in the text or supplemental file is shown.

BioStudies. All metadata fields are indexed and available for search, including advanced search by combining search criteria and patterns. Faceted search for fields indexed for a particular data collection is provided, and ontology-assisted search that employs Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO¹) is available.

2.1.4 Synthesis

There has been increasing effort to enhance the findability of the long tail of data. General purpose repositories such as Zenodo are utilized by authors and publishers alike to store and access datasets that have no home in a specialist repository and efforts via SIBiLS, Europe PMC and BioStudies to enhance supplementary files have been made. However, there are limits to the success due to a number of factors:

- The assignment of PIDs has become systematic, however it is at the record-level rather than the file-level.
- The focus on DOIs by the publishing community has caused a detrimental effect on the mainstay identifiers of life sciences, accessions.
- Although publishers have embraced the DOI, their internal validation systems appear to have not caught up to capture DataCite DOIs (focussing on Crossref infrastructure).
- There is limited success in enabling citation of supplementary data files in their own right as datasets.

¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/>

- The effective use and completion of metadata standard is observed when it is enforced by data repositories during the deposition process, but less effective for supplementary data files requested by publishers.
- Specialized search engines in datasets exist when metadata is available, but in their absence text mining is necessary prior to indexing.

2.2 Accessibility

« Datasets should be accessible through a clearly defined access procedure, ideally using automated means. Metadata should always remain accessible, even when the data is no longer available. »

2.2.1 Machine accessibility

Zenodo. Zenodo provides developer solutions for searching and downloading records. Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the open OAI-PMH protocol. The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary. At the time of this report, 95.1% of datasets deposited in Zenodo have an Open Access status, 4.3% are restricted, and 0.6% are under embargo. Finally, Zenodo also offers REST APIs to search published records and download files directly. Currently there is no SPARQL endpoint, limiting the ability for developers to query data using a standardized query language.

DataCite. As a DOI registry agency, all DOIs and their associated metadata are available via their REST API. This will include all DOIs registered from Zenodo, Dryad and FigShare as well as other repositories utilising the DataCite DOI system.

PMC. PMC does not provide REST APIs for supplementary files, direct access to supplementary files requires FTP (see <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pub/filespec-delivery/>). Files could be uniquely identified by their names, but they are discretionary and have no standardization; PMC only states that "names of image files and supplemental data files must match the names referenced in the XML file". A robust approach for obtaining PIDs at file-level involves combining the record identifier with the file name. Unfortunately, this practice is not standard.

Europe PMC. Europe PMC provides access to supplementary files by REST API, as well as by bulk download through FTP. Filenames reflect those provided by the publisher and as with PMC are not standardised. Supplementary files are text mined for accessions and biomedical entities. The fragment in which the entity is situated is also returned by the API, as well as the type of entity (eg gene/protein, disease, species). APIs are available to return either all entities found in a specific article or articles, or all text mined entities of a particular type found within a particular article section (eg, all accession numbers identified within the supplementary material).

2.2.2 File types

Presentation of analysis. The use of proprietary file types can hinder accessibility and machine readability. To assess the prevalence of different file types, we filtered Zenodo's search results to include only "Datasets" and then analyzed the file types associated with

these records. We conducted a similar analysis for PMC, focusing on supplementary data files. As Zenodo does not contain depositions prior to 2014, we limited our PMC analysis to records from that year onward. Table 1 presents the results.

File type	% in Zenodo datasets	% in PMC supp files
zip	24.5%	13.6%
glb	17.2%	0.0%
jpg	15.6%	20.1%
xlsx	12.9%	12.8%
csv	12.4%	0.9%
txt	9.6%	0.6%
pdf	6.6%	45.0%
png	3.2%	0.8%
docx	3.1%	32.1%
html	0.8%	1.2%

Table 1. Percentage of Zenodo and PMC records containing a selection of file types.

Comparison. The most frequent file type in Zenodo is zip, but it is impossible to know what these files actually contain. glb files, a type of 3-Dimensions file format, are second in Zenodo, but totally absent from PMC. Then comes jpg, but the most interesting file types follow:

- open file types, preferable for machine readability, are much more present in Zenodo than in PMC: 12.4% versus 0.9% for csv, 9.6% versus 0.6% for txt.
- xls files, a proprietary format, is found equally in both
- some other proprietary formats are much more present in PMC: 45% versus 6.6% for pdf, 32.1% versus 3.1% for docx.

Widespread use of Excel files. This comparison has strong limits, as it is unknown if these supplementary data files really contain datasets, instead of complementary narratives. Yet, in a previous work (Gobeill et al., 2024), accession numbers from Global Core Biodata Resources in PMC publications were searched. The experiment revealed that 97% of the identified accession numbers were published in supplementary data. Regarding the file types, since 2014, 87% of these accession numbers were in Excel files, with a resurgence of the old xls format (14%), which is considered as deprecated. An addition of 5% of these identified accession numbers were published in docx or doc files. While Excel is a widely user-friendly tool for data manipulation and analysis, extracting structured data from Excel files often requires specialized text extraction techniques. Issues such as encoding or merged cells can further complicate this process, potentially leading to data loss or inconsistencies. This can hinder data accessibility, interoperability, and long-term preservation. Despite the convenience of Excel for researchers with limited computing skills, there can be a disconnect between the informal requests of reviewers or publishers for supplementary data and the formal requirements for FAIR deposition. This can leave authors in a challenging position, unsure of how to best prepare and share their data in a FAIR compliant manner. While many scientists have positive attitudes towards data sharing and reuse, they face challenges in data management and storage practices (Tenopir et al., 2020).

2.2.3 Long-term preservation

Zenodo. Zenodo is supported by long-term funding sources, it receives ongoing funding from the European Commission through Horizon Europe, ensuring its continued operation.

PMC. PMC, as a service of the National Institutes of Health (NIH), benefits from consistent funding from the U.S. government. In parallel to the supplementary data files, PMC allows deposition in a curated list of "suitable public data repository"; out of the 147 proposed in their grid, 118 are designated as having "sustained support," indicating their commitment to long-term data preservation.

Europe PMC. Europe PMC is supported by 35 funders contributing to one grant, managed by Wellcome. This grant is renewed on a 5-year basis. EMBL-EBI also provides in-kind funding in the form of infrastructure provision as well as some staffing.

BioStudies. EMBL-EBI resources are supported by a mixed core and grant funding model. While individual resources rely partly on external funding sources, institutional funds can offer continuity of key staff and the data contained in resources. Technical and administrative infrastructure are centralised and institutionally funded functions at EMBL-EBI, ensuring resilience of the data resources both with respect to user-facing services and hardware backend (redundant servers, backups). Together these measures mitigate risks from external funding discontinuation and ensure data preservation.

Dryad. Dryad is a US-led international repository, funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF). It is supported by a membership model as well as submission fees to ensure the preservation of archived data.

2.2.4 Synthesis

- Zenodo, PMC and Europe PMC offer comprehensive developer solutions for accessing data.
- The widespread use of proprietary formats for sharing data, such as Excel, hinders the principles of FAIR.
- The most popular format in Zenodo is zip, which raises questions about how submission requirements are enforced.
- Both Zenodo and PMC are supported by long-term funding sources, ensuring their continued operation and data preservation.

2.3 Interoperability

« Data and metadata are conceptualized, expressed and structured using common, published standards. »

2.3.1 Normalized way to identify and represent entities

As life sciences research generates increasingly complex and diverse datasets, there is a greater need for standardized ways to represent and understand the data. Controlled vocabularies and ontologies, and accession numbers, facilitate data interoperability, consistency and sharing, making it easier to integrate and analyze data from different sources. Furthermore, advances in data management and analysis tools have made it easier to incorporate controlled vocabularies and accession numbers into research workflows (Smith, 2021).

Analysis. To quantify the increase in controlled vocabulary and accession numbers usage in publications, Gobeill et al., 2024 searched for identifiers from Global Core Biodata Resources (such as UniProt, Ensembl, or Gene Ontology) in the PMC supplementary data files. It has already been mentioned that 97% of all these mentions were found in the supplementary data files. Regular expressions were employed to match identifiers, sourced from the Identifiers.org Central Registry. Stringent criteria were implemented, requiring the resource name to precede the identifier, achieving a high precision of 99%, but probably many false negatives. As depicted in Figure 3, the results reveal a dramatic rise since the early 2020s, with mentions increasing from 3 million in 2020 to 33 million in the first half of 2024 alone.

Figure 3. Evolution of GCBR identifiers in the PMC supplementary data files.

Discussion. This illustrates that authors are increasingly sharing and identifying data, which aligns with FAIR principles. This trend is encouraging, as it facilitates the work of biocurators by providing standardized data that can be more easily integrated into public databases and knowledge repositories. Finally, at the metadata level, Zenodo enforces the use of open, external vocabularies, such as for license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE).

2.3.2 Data formats

Annotated text data with BioC. BioC (Bioinformatics Common Format) is particularly well-suited for sharing annotations at the text level (Comeau et al., 2013) and it offers a more minimalist approach compared to other formats. Despite its simplicity, BioC provides a powerful and versatile framework for representing biological annotations within life sciences publications. As illustrated in Figure 5, BioC enables the sharing of annotations at various levels, including sentence, section, or document, with mandatory offset and length specifications. However, while BioC excels in representing annotation metadata, it lacks a formal structure for formatting full-text and metadata themselves.

Europe PMC and W3C. Europe PMC provides annotations in a number of formats. Using the REST API, they can be requested in XML, JSON or JSON-LD (JSON for Linking Data) format. The latter option provides annotations in the format described in the W3C recommendation “Web Annotation Data Model” (W3C, 2017). This is a standardised model for describing the relationship between a ‘body’ and ‘target’ document. In the context of annotations, this allows an annotation provider to assert a link between a text fragment relating to a particular entity in the target document and a ‘body’ document which describes that entity. JSON-LD is a lightweight serialisation format for describing links between documents intended for use in web APIs (Sporny et al. 2020). The annotation model provides multiple options for specifying

a text fragment, including character offsets, XPath and CSS selectors, and quoting the text with a prefix and suffix to disambiguate multiple instances of the same phrase.

Linked Data. A recent NISO standard (NISO, 2024) is an application of HTML and JSON-LD to create semantic relationships between content and data elements in scholarly publishing to express self-describing, machine-actionable content for reuse and interchange of scholarly research information. The format description defines a set of rules that outline the minimal characteristics of documents (Linked Documents) that conform to the standard and a mechanism to define more detailed Content Profiles to extend and refine the rules for specific use cases. CP/LD does not have to replace existing models used for journal articles, books, data sets, or semantic and metadata schemes. Instead, these can be transformed as needed to CP/LD, enabling the combination of arbitrary portions of content, data, semantics, and other resources from separate sources into a single, standards-based format optimized for interchange, search, and display (NISO, 2024).

Pensoft and JATS XML. For publications, the most established is JATS (Journal Article Tag Suite; <https://jats.nlm.nih.gov/>), a XML-based format for representing journal articles, which is requested from publishers for integration in PMC.

Annotated text data in JATS publications. Publications can be enhanced through the integration of annotations. These annotations can be requested from authors by publishers, or generated by third parties annotators, or by data platforms using text mining techniques. However, the sharing of annotated publications remains a significant challenge. Many contacted publishers express reluctance to include annotations in their Version of Record, citing the subjective and temporal nature of annotations, and often preferring to distribute them as ancillary files. Nevertheless, at least one publisher advocates for integrating annotations directly into the JATS format. While JATS includes a tag for annotations, it currently supports only free-text annotations at the document level. This publisher prefers a more granular approach, integrating annotations within the text using XML tags. However, this format can pose challenges for data platforms, which may struggle to accurately extract and utilize these nested XML tags and there is no standard tagging recommendation via a working group such as JAT4R, which would enhance interoperability cross platform.

Annotated text data in other formats. While JATS and JSON are commonly recommended formats, our interviews with key actors highlight that format selection is often driven by specific use cases. For instance, one publisher favors the HuggingFace format to streamline data preparation for subsequent machine learning tasks. Another publisher prefers the CP/LD format for its suitability in displaying annotated documents in its interface. A prominent data platform has chosen the Web Annotation Data Model in ancillary files for its flexibility. Finally, Zenodo utilizes JSON Schema as its internal metadata representation, offering export to popular formats like Dublin Core or MARCXML.

2.3.3 Synthesis

- Controlled vocabularies and accession numbers are increasingly used to identify entities in articles and datasets, enhancing retrieval effectiveness - in particular recall - and interoperability.
- While the JATS format has become well-established for sharing publications, there is no recognized format for sharing annotated text data. Although the BioC format has emerged as a promising candidate, its adoption has been limited.

- The format used by key actors for sharing annotated text data is often influenced by its specific use cases and needs, leading to a fragmented landscape.

2.4 Reusability

« Characteristics of data and their provenance are described in detail according to domain-relevant community standards, with clear and accessible conditions for use. »

2.4.1 Documentation

Documentation in Zenodo. Inadequate documentation can make it difficult for others to understand how data was generated, processed, and analyzed, limiting its reusability. For Zenodo datasets, README files often provide essential information, including purpose, contents, and usage instructions. Additionally, data dictionaries, either standalone or embedded within Excel sheets, can be found. Zenodo ensures traceability of all uploaded data and metadata to registered users. Metadata can optionally specify original authors. At the annotation level, ECO codes provide a standardized way to describe the evidence supporting annotations, and has become increasingly widely used in life sciences to document annotations and datasets (Chibucos et al., 2017).

Documentation in PMC and Europe PMC. Supplemental files are associated with the research article and it is assumed by providers that the context is found within the article and human readers are the users. This limits the utility of machines to understand what the supplemental file contains.

2.4.2 Licenses

Introduction. Restrictive licensing terms can significantly hinder the reusability of data by limiting its use and sharing. Recent funder policies have played a pivotal role in driving the transition towards more Open Access articles and datasets. To assess this trend, we analyzed the evolution of licenses attached to PMC articles in the last ten years.

Figure 4. Evolution of licenses in PubMed Central.

Analysis of licenses in PMC. Although PMC is a literature resource, as demonstrated throughout this article it contains much of the long tail of data - supplementary files. These

files follow the license of the article, unless otherwise stated, which is very uncommon if it exists at all. CC-BY licenses have consistently demonstrated their favorability for reusability, with a slight increase from 68% to 72% over the past decade. A positive trend for FAIR principles is the decline of missing or non-standard licenses (NO-CC), which favors clear information and permissive licenses. Conversely, licenses that restrict commercial use (NC) have risen from 20% to 27%. The highly permissive CC0 license, which does not require attribution, has become less common.

Finally, despite the ostensible Open Access nature of PubMed Central (PMC), machine accessibility remains sometimes constrained. A significant portion of PMC articles is accessible to humans to read, through the search engine, but copyright restrictions on text mining limit the availability of their JATS XML format and thus the supplementary files. This constraint significantly hinders the reusability of these files for computational analysis.

2.4.3 Synthesis

- The Evidence and Conclusion Ontology (ECO) has become increasingly widely used in life sciences to document annotations and datasets.
- CC-BY licenses have become increasingly popular for reusability, while NO-CC licenses have declined, suggesting a positive trend for FAIR principles. However, the rise in NC licenses indicates a growing preference for limiting commercial use.
- Text mining limitations for some Open Access articles highlight the conflict between the FAIR principles and copyright restrictions.

3. Opportunities for improving

There has been significant progress over time towards FAIR data, and it has garnered much attention, effort and recommended practices. The long tail of data, in the form of article supplemental files and data deposited to general purpose repositories, is increasing in volume and increasingly being assigned persistent identifiers, although to a limited degree for supplemental files. However, there are many limitations to its full utility and incorporation into effective pipelines to assist scientific progress. Below we provide some recommendations to improve the situation, for each of the actors in this space.

3.1 General recommendations

All stakeholders have different roles and responsibilities within the process, but there are some general recommendations that apply to everyone.

- Do not publish a dataset unless it has a unique persistent identifier that can be used to locate it.
- Ensure the data is published on an appropriate archiving platform that will maintain its sustainability.
- Ensure an open license is used (CC0 or CCBY) and clearly identified within the metadata of the dataset in a machine readable format.
- Where possible, incorporate metadata using established schemas, ontologies and standards that will enable its incorporation with other relevant data and literature.

3.2 Recommendations for funders/institutions

- Require data associated with the outputs of the research to be made openly available and published under an open license on an appropriate data repository

3.3 Recommendations for authors / publishers

- Do not publish data as supplemental files (limit supplemental files to materials other than datasets) and clearly identify what the supplemental file is.
- Utilize resources such as Cell Press STAR★Methods (Marcus, 2016) to ensure materials and methods contain fundamental information (such as protein or gene species, cell lines, etc) and Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research (Arguillas et al 2022) to improve content standards.
- Encourage authors to release data before publication of the final version of record publication.
- Guide authors to high quality databases for submission of data (eg <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/recommended-repositories> or Study on the readiness of research data and literature repositories to facilitate compliance with the Open Science Horizon Europe MGA requirements, Lazzeri, 2024).
- Useful reference
 - *Omics Data Publishing to International Repositories from Australia* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10147703>
- Mandate authors to publish FAIR associated data under an open license. Authors could be assisted:
 - by data librarians (like in University of Geneva, which has a dedicated service to support researchers in depositing FAIR data)
 - by FAIRification tools (e.g. FAIR-by-Design)

3.4 Recommendations for curators

A curator is a FAIR-ificator: sequence deposition is a good example of a good data lifecycle management effort. For machine learning and scalable curation, curators are encouraged to:

- Produce passage-centric annotation rather than paper-centric.
- Keep track of negative examples (e.g. articles that are not relevant to a given curation)

Solutions should be simple and not hinder the curator's work.

3.5 Recommendations for data platforms

- Adopt standards for data sharing
- Reference databases must be agile to fix inconsistencies

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